

ORGANIZING MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS IN HIGH SCHOOLS

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Annotation: this article provides detailed information about reforms in the field of culture, art, and music in our country, methods of organizing music culture lessons in secondary schools, and various methods used by music culture teachers in lessons.

Keywords: music, culture, student, interest, mind, lesson, method, school, theory, pedagogy.

Annotatsiya: mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizdagi madaniyat, san'at, musiqa sohasidagi islohotlar, umumta'lim maktablarida musiqa madaniyati darslarini tashkil etish usullari, musiqa madaniyati fani o'qituvchilariga darslarda foydalaniladigan turli xil metodlar haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, madaniyat, o'quvchi, qiziqish, ong, dars, metod, maktab, nazariya, pedagogika.

Аннотация: в данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в сфере культуры, искусства и музыки в нашей стране, методах организации уроков музыкальной культуры в общеобразовательных школах, а также различных методах, используемых учителями музыкальной культуры на уроках.

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, ученик, интерес, сознание, урок, метод, школа, теория, педагогика.

In the course of music lessons in secondary schools, it is necessary to inculcate the sense of patriotism in students by singing songs. A person who has a homeland will be proud and have high goals and objectives. Today, instilling the universal spirituality and national values of the Uzbek people, which have been formed over the centuries, is of great importance in educating young people to become patriotic and well-rounded people. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1].

In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the

efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3]. The educational subject “Music culture” is connected with all educational subjects taught in general secondary schools, including literature, fine arts, physical education, work and other subjects. Along with all academic subjects, music education has also introduced state education standard, which allows full use of national musical heritage. These are practical folk tunes and songs, creative activities of singers and musicians. Makom, shashmakom are reflected in epics and today’s modern music.

A modern music teacher should be highly cultured, have unlimited devotion to his profession, and possess advanced pedagogical thinking. He must have the ability to continuously develop his professional culture. He needs to have deep knowledge and skills in the fields of music, sophistication, pedagogy and psychology-physiology, in particular, music teaching methodology. Especially, in the profession of a music teacher, the qualities of playing an instrument, singing, conducting a choir, and theorizing music should be embodied to the required extent. He must have a perfect knowledge of national music and the Uzbek literary language, be familiar with universal music culture, and everyday musical and cultural life.[4]

A music teacher should be a master of pedagogical communication and have the ability to effectively use the methods of pedagogical influence in any situation. A music teacher should be a scientific thinker, a creator of advanced experiences, inquisitive and creative, and strive to discover new forms and methods of music education.

It is necessary to connect and enrich the content of music education with the content of other subjects and everyday life. The advanced experience and new methods discovered by the inquisitive and creative teacher are the main support and source of inspiration for the continuous improvement and development of music education in the school.

A knowledgeable and experienced music teacher, as an art intellectual, is the head of music education work in the school. The basic foundation of a student's musical culture is formed in primary school. But preschool education has an independent importance as an important and responsible period of human personality formation, because it is a preparatory stage of primary education. Primary school music lessons include simple musical knowledge, understanding and skills that are in line with the standards of children's mental development. Through listening to music, singing, dancing, playing simple

instruments, artistic perception, talking about the impressions and knowledge gained from music, artistic evaluation of the work, and the development of musical creativity skills, students will develop a passion for music and an artistic need.[5]

In the course of education, students will acquire knowledge and skills about: Children's songs, musical games, dances and songs, our graceful national instruments (grade 1); Solitude; musical instrument; what's the tune The expressive language of melody; Types of musical instruments (musical instruments); melody and method, repetition of tempo, melody, its constant and variable return, stanza and refrain; Uzbek folk music; popular folk songs (alla, yalla, lapar, terma, sing me) and popular tunes; Uzbek professional music (singing, big singing); understanding of composer's musical creation; folk music in the work of composers.

In the course of practical training in the content of the subject, notation, the structure of simple tunes is studied as an example, the initial skills of singing according to the note are formed.

So, the role of music in cultural life is important, and in the implementation of musical education, it is one of the urgent tasks of the teacher to effectively organize classes with full understanding of its main goals and tasks.[6]

Music pedagogy, methodological and material support, music folklore, children with limited talent, inheritance, specific characteristics, mixed lesson, active, emotional effect, spiritual effect, educational concept, owner of pedagogical thinking, artistic need, artistic assessment, invariable and variable repetition, note-to-note singing. The educational subject of musical culture serves to form the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of students, to implement the education of national pride and patriotism, to develop skill, sophistication, artistic taste, to expand the range of thought, to educate independence and initiative. The educational subject of music culture is connected with all academic subjects taught in general education schools, including literature, visual arts, physical education, work and other subjects.

These are reflected in popular folk tunes and songs, creative activities of singers and musicians, status, shashmaqom, epics, and today's modern musical activity. Such possibilities of musical art serve as a unique and unrepeatable resource in educating the new generation and in their development. The new educational content of music education based on the state educational standards ensures the development of students' musical knowledge and skills, such as

observation, memory strengthening, visual imagination, creativity, independence, initiative, artistic and musical taste.

For the musical aesthetic development of students, the teacher should prepare seriously in his work and ensure that the lessons are conducted at a high methodical level. After all, the lesson requires the teacher to have a lot of willpower, research, responsiveness, and quick reaction to various pedagogical situations. An ineffective, unsuccessful lesson, shortcomings do not give the teacher peace and happiness for a long time, he feels the need to look back and look for the reasons. The lesson of music culture is the main form of organizing music education at school. Although musical clubs and optional classes are also in practice, the lesson never loses its importance.

Music culture lessons include various forms of musical activity. These are public collective speech, performing musical rhythmic movements, listening to music, literacy, musical creativity, playing children's musical instruments. Music lessons are different from other subject lessons because they are artistic, interesting and stimulate more creative pleasure, emotional feelings and imaginative experiences in children. Music, especially, has a great positive effect on the mental and moral development of children. After all, "it is impossible to adequately educate children without musical education". Therefore, music lessons are, first of all, an educational lesson. Artistic education is its logical content.

Music lessons differ in the following features:

First, it consists of various examples of music history, theory and performance, choir training, music literacy, listening to music, music analysis and literature, children's musical instrument playing, rhythmic movements. Therefore, it is a mixed class.

Secondly, music differs from other forms of art in its means of expression, its "language". If fiction, artistic words, visual arts are expressed by colors and graphic lines, dance, artistic movements, then music is expressed by means of melody created in musical sounds. If we perceive works of art and sculpture by seeing, fiction by reading and hearing, cinema and theater by seeing and hearing, we can perceive music only by listening attentively.

It is not for nothing that even blind people are able to develop talented musicians. "Only a musical ear can evoke a musical feeling". Music is an art that communicates with a precise measure of time. The piece will not be perfectly understood if you don't tune in to the tempo of the music being played and listen to every element of it. Therefore, when we re-listen to classical works, we feel its

new artistic aspects. It's hard to put into words the emotions expressed through music. "When words fail, music comes to the rescue".

Thirdly, music has an active aesthetic effect on children, makes them happy, and evokes positive experiences. Children are cheerful, happy and have fun from a good, meaningful and interesting music lesson. So, even if the music lesson is scheduled for the last lesson, the children will have a rest and their fatigue will dissipate.

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